

REVIEW ARTICLE

UNDERSTANDING LAND SUBSIDENCE THROUGH CASE STUDY OF JAKARTA, INDONESIA

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Abstract:

A disaster is a catastrophic event that causes damage and loss of life and property and severely affects the social, cultural, and economic life of the people. Natural and Man-made are two categories of disasters. Natural disasters include floods, earthquakes, land sinking, etc, man-made disasters are fires, accidents, terrorism, etc. that solely happen due to man's ignorance. Some disasters are a combination of both natural and man-made disasters, these include land subsidence, urban floods, etc. Disaster triggers might vary, but the phenomenon and the impact vaguely remain the same. In today's world, where cities are growing, large-scale development is taking place and with this, the density of the cities is getting denser and denser, as a result, the demand for resources is increasing rapidly. Urbanization, the unsustainable use of resources, and haphazard development have caused many disasters in the past, and they continue to happen. One such phenomenon that is prevalent and has impacted many cities is Land Subsidence or Land Sinking. Many Countries, such as Jakarta, Indonesia; San Joaquin Valley, California; Mexico City, Mexico; Kawajima, Japan Joshimath, India; etc. Jakarta is the capital city of Indonesia, which is experiencing land subsidence and it is estimated that it will sink completely by 2050. This paper intends to find out the reasons that lead to the present situation of land subsidence in both the cities and the role of different development agencies in the development of the city is also covered. The later part of the paper will make suggestions to improve the existing situation of the town.

Keywords: Land Subsidence, Disaster, Mitigation.

Introduction:

Disaster is a catastrophic event that causes loss of life, property, and economy. The Disaster Management Act, of 2005 defines disaster as "a catastrophe, mishap, calamity or grave occurrence in any

area, arising from natural or manmade causes, or by accident or negligence which results in substantial loss of life or human suffering or damage to, and destruction of, property, or damage to, or degradation of, environment, and is of such a nature or magnitude as to be beyond the coping capacity of the community of the affected area". Disaster is of two types: Natural Disasters and Man-Made Disaster. Natural are the ones, which occur naturally, without the intervention of humans. They can be geological or metrological events that have the potential to cause loss of life and property at a large scale, for example, earthquakes, landslides, floods, wildfires, drought, hurricanes, etc. Man-made Disasters are caused due to human interventions, these include industrial accidents, stampedes, terrorism, fires, building disasters, disease outbreaks, etc. There is another type of disaster, known as the Hybrid Disaster, which is caused due to natural and man-made reasons. Land Subsidence can be classified as one such disaster.

Land subsidence is a phenomenon in which a part of or an area of land caves in, or in other words, the area of land sinks in, and its elevation decreases. As per USGS Science for Changing World, "Land subsidence is a gradual settling or sudden sinking of the Earth's surface due to removal or displacement of subsurface earth materials" (Water Resources Mission Area, 2019). Land subsidence refers to the gradual term "land subsidence" and describes the slow or fast sinking of the Earth's surface brought on by the removal or shifting of subsurface materials. The land may settle downward due to a variety of causes, including sinkhole development, soil compaction, erosion, seismic activity, and glacial isostatic adjustment. The usual causes of subsidence include resource extraction operations like drilling, pumping, and mineral extraction—basically, any process that obstructs the ground's natural flow of gas, oil, or water. Seismic activity, soil compaction, glacial isostatic adjustment, weathering, ground cavity formation, and the addition of water to fine soils are examples of natural causes of subsidence. There are a few cases around the world witnessing the same phenomenon, Jakarta, Indonesia is one such example

Jakarta is the capital city of Indonesia. It lies on the northwest coast of the Java Sea. It is situated on the northern coastal alluvial plane of Jawa which shares boundaries with West Jawa Province in the south and the east, and with Banten Province in the west. The city is expanding rapidly and is also counted as one of the coastal megacities around the world. Located on the north coast, it faces busy shipping lanes of the Java Sea. Jakarta is the largest metropolitan city with a population of 10.2 million, inhabiting an area of 660 sq.km. In 1930, the city's population was 533,015 which grew to 2.9 million in 1961, the population increased by 2.4 million in 31 years. Jakarta's population was 8.2 million. The population growth rate is high, with a 2.5% growth rate in 1980-90. This points towards rapid urbanization. Also as per the reports, it is one of the fastest-growing and urbanizing cities in Indonesia with rapid growth in Industry, trade, transportation, real estate, and many others. Jakarta is a lowland area with five landforms, which include an Alluvial Landform in the southern part; a Marine Origin Landform in the Northern Part, which is adjacent to the coastal line; a Beach Ridge Landform, towards the northwest and northeast part; a Swamp and mangrove swamp landforms at coastal fringe; Former channels which are perpendicular to the coastline. About 13 natural and artificial waterbodies and 2 canals flow through the city, and their tributaries form the main drainage system of the city. Aquifers present in the city range from 40 to 250m in depth. The city is essential to both the national government and the economy. Urban area development is a reaction to Jakarta City's rapid population increase. The city is facing significant challenges of urban

growth and uncontrolled pollution. Jakarta is highly vulnerable to land subsidence disasters. The reason for Jakarta to be known as the fastest-sinking city in the world.

The History of Sinking

The history of land subsidence in Jakarta dates back to the 18th century. The occurrence of subsidence came to light in 1926, as evidence was found by repeated leveling that was conducted in the northern part of the city. Unfortunately, the investigation was put at a halt for 50 years. It came to light in 1978 that the land subsidence in the city accelerated and became a prominent problem. Continuous monitoring of the levels from 1982-1997, it was found that the city sank by 20-200 cm in several places in the city. Currently, North Jakarta has sunk by 250 mm in the last 10 years and continues to sink by 250mm a year in some parts. The groundwater level of aquifers continues to decline in several locations in Jakarta. During 2002-07 alone, the groundwater level declined from 0.2 to 2m per year. The changes in groundwater level are dynamic, which occurred in a short period, whereas, this short-term variation has led to long-term subsidence phenomena in the city.

The Cause of Sinking

The reason behind the sinking is controlled by four factors, which combine and cause the sinking. They are: Groundwater extraction, construction load, natural consolidation of the soil, and tectonic factors. The first is the geological condition of the city, which is dominated by groundwater extraction. This includes physiography and geology. The city is located near the Java Sea, at just 8m (26 feet) above sea level. It lies on the low and flat alluvial plain that is swampy, i.e. the soil is loosely packed. Another reason is the creation of voids due to the extraction of groundwater.

Approximately 64% of the total population of the city relies on groundwater for its needs, being it a cheaper and more convenient source of water than the piped water supply. Though, there are 13 water bodies, that are present in the city, most of these are polluted and the water is not fit for drinking or usable for any purpose. Since the groundwater is accessible easily and a cheaper source, it has been extracted for many years. Extraction of groundwater over the years has led to the drainage of the aquifers, which has led to the sinking of the ground. This phenomenon can be understood easily through Figure 1, in which it is clearly visible that the land is directly affected by water pumping from the ground. It has sunken, affecting the surrounding areas as well. Similarly, figure 2 depicts the effect of land subsidence on urban population, where the buildings tend to submerge in the ground. The load of the built-up tends to put pressure on the ground, which adds on to the sinking, and the subsidence further affects the population in many ways.

The subsidence is severe in Jakarta due high density, elevation and presence of waterbodies. The disaster is severe in urban areas with high density and area where the water table is high. The sinking often leads to flooding, which can be understood through figure 3. In this, the part above depicts land and a low-level water body, in the contrasting side, the below part of the figure depicts a sunken area of the land, which has accumulated water. The water must have seeped in from the nearby waterbody, which in this case has caused floods. This is what exactly happened in the city.

For both the national government and the economy, Jakarta is essential. The growing population of Jakarta City has prompted the development of urban regions. As a result, it has emerged as a catalyst for several environmental issues in this decade. Many urban areas have a density ranging between 11,000-19,000 people/sq km, where the highest population density was found in central Jakarta. From the standpoint of population density, the rate of land subsidence increases with population density. The

population and population density are directly correlated. As a result, the annual rise in population has a significant impact on the growing number of inhabitants. An instance of human actions leading to land subsidence is the over-extraction of groundwater. The greater the population density in a given location, the greater the need for clean water to support their livelihoods.

Figure 1: Land Subsidence due to Water Extraction

Figure 2: Effect on Urban Built-up

Figure 3: Land Subsidence

Impact of Sinking

In general, the sinking has impacted the city and it is evident in various forms, such as damage to the structures and infrastructure, particularly cracking of concrete structures, change and roads, and tilting of the structures, particularly residential structures, which have been affected the most. There are changes evidently seen, such as changes in river canal and drain flow systems.

Figure 4: Impact on North Jakarta

The subsidence has also increased inland seawater intrusions. The subsidence is prominent in North Jakarta, as can be seen in Figure 4, where the most affected districts are- Mutiara Beach, Cengkareng, and Cakung districts.

These impacts can be classified into the following categories: -

1. Economic Impact: Land subsidence has a large and complex effect on Jakarta's economy, resulting in both direct and indirect expenses and far-reaching effects. The main impacted areas are broken down as follows:

Infrastructure Damage: Subsidence cracks and weakens roads, bridges, canals, and other critical infrastructure, requiring constant repair and maintenance, leading to substantial financial burdens. Figure 5 represents effect of land subsidence on roads, leading to formation of cracks and fissures.

Figure 5: Effect on Infrastructure

Increased Flooding: As land subsidence, the risk of flooding intensifies, inundating homes, businesses, and industrial areas, causing property damage, disrupting operations, and displacing people. This results in lost productivity, revenue, and tax income. **Saline water intrusion:** Subsidence allows seawater to penetrate further inland, contaminating freshwater sources and agricultural land, impacting food security and livelihoods. Figure 6 represents the intrusion or flooding of saline water in the low-lying area.

Figure 6: Flooding due to Subsidence

Coastal Erosion: Subsidence exacerbates coastal erosion, threatening coastal communities and infrastructure, leading to property loss, displacement, and damage to tourism, a vital sector for Jakarta's economy. Figure 7 explains the phenomenon of coastal soil erosion.

Figure 7: Coastal Erosion

A 2015 study by the World Bank estimated that land subsidence could cost Jakarta \$35 billion annually by 2050 if left unchecked. Another study by the Indonesian National Institute of Sciences (LIPI) estimated that the total economic losses due to subsidence in Jakarta could reach \$42 billion by 2040.

2. Social Impact: Land subsidence in Jakarta has significant social ramifications that affect all of the city's different groups, making it more than simply an economic concern. Here's a deeper look at the lives it affects:

Increased Vulnerability and Displacement: Unequal Burden: Communities of color who live in substandardly built homes in low-lying locations are frequently the most affected by landslides and flooding brought on by subsidence. They don't have the resources to rebuild or migrate, which makes them more vulnerable and causes them to be uprooted from their homes.

Disrupted Livelihoods: Flooding affected the revenue and food security by destroying marketplaces, enterprises, and agricultural land. Women in particular who work in the informal economy lost their jobs and find it difficult to start over.

Health Risks: Standing floodwaters give rise to mosquito breeding grounds, which raises the possibility of contracting dengue fever, malaria, and other watery illnesses. Healthcare systems are additionally burdened by poor cleanliness.

Apart from these, a race for securing resources, such as land, water, and housing is intensified, and the rise of competition for resources leads to social tension and conflict between different socio-economic groups of society. Additionally, the scarcity of habitable land loss of livelihood, and fear of displacement further attack the victims mentally. The fear of loss of heritage and historical structures has a similar impact on the community.

3. Environmental Impact: Land subsidence in Jakarta has a large and diverse environmental impact on ecosystems, water, and land. Below is a summary of the main issues:

Degradation of Land: Increased Risk of Flooding arises when land declines, which can submerge low-lying regions, riverbanks, and coastal areas. This results in: Salinization, in which the infiltration of saline water contaminates agricultural land and freshwater supplies, influencing crop yields and soil fertility, which in turn affects food security and livelihoods Coastal erosion, exacerbated by subsidence, poses significant threats to coastal ecosystems, including beaches, mangroves, and biodiversity. This process results in the loss of habitat and a reduction in biodiversity, impacting the delicate balance of coastal ecosystems. Subsidence intensifies the effects of coastal erosion, further endangering these vital natural resources and ecosystems.

Waterlogging: Standing water gives mosquitoes and other disease-carrying insects a place to breed, raising the risk of illness and harming ecosystems.

Current Situation:

Land Subsidence is one of the results of increasing development in Jakarta. The demand for land has increased due to urbanisation, thus making the city vulnerable to various kinds of environmental problems. Jakarta is a very important city in terms of political and economic perspective. The prevalent factors have resulted in increasing potential land subsidence in Jakarta. Some areas, namely Mutiara Beach sinking by 8.5-10.9 cm/year, has a population density of 8,635 people/Km²; Cengkareng is experiencing subsidence ranging from 10-17.5 cm/year, has a population density of 19,363 people/Km²; Cakung is sinking by 7.5-9.5 cm/year, it has a population density of 11,919 people/Km². Central Jakarta Cakung is one of the suburbs in the city, where the major land use is residential, 45%, and industrial 24%, located in the eastern part of Jakarta. The district has a strong transportation network, with industrial and commercial as dominant land-use. Cengkareng is a developed district, where dense village settlements are prominent land-use. Due to dense settlement, the load on the soil is greater and has impacted the soil compression, giving a rise in compression thus resulting in land subsidence. Collectively, the areas with high density put more pressure on the infrastructure and demand for more resources, one such demand which inflicts land subsidence is groundwater extraction. Thus, when more volume of groundwater declines, the pressure from the surface increases, and subsidence increases significantly. If the same pattern is followed, it is believed that Jakarta will be submerged underwater completely by 2050. Currently, the average rate of sinking is 10-150 mm per year across different areas and the highest rate is 110-120mm per year, particularly in coastal areas. The extreme rate of subsidence is observed within the city, which is up to 175 mm per year. Figure 8 depicts the subsidence rate over the years from 1997 till 2050 projected).

Figure 8: land Subsidence over the years

The figure is very important in context to understand the location, impact, and intensity of disasters during history. In 2007, Jakarta saw severe floods, resulting in 76 deaths and half a million flood victims. The flood affected 35km of coastline in the northern part of the city, affecting 4 million inhabitants, which is already sinking by 75mm per year, and affected by frequent floods. Due to this 40% of the city is below the sea level.

Mitigation Measures

To combat the problem of land subsidence, the government has come up with a contentious and ambitious plan The Great Garuda, also known as the National Capital Integrated Coastal Development (NCICD) Masterplan in Jakarta, Indonesia.

The Great Garuda proposes a massive 40-kilometer-long and a 24-meter-high barrier designed like Indonesia's national emblem, the magnificent Garuda bird. This defensive barrier would surround Jakarta Bay, sheltering it from the oncoming ocean. But the plan does not end there. Within this protected embrace, 17 new islands would develop, reclaimed land ready for houses, companies, and industries that could accommodate up to 300,000 people. The city's critical infrastructure would also get a facelift, with new drainage systems, water treatment facilities, and transit networks to ensure seamless operation. To bring this great vision to life, green areas such as parks and wetlands would be weaved in, improving the environment and providing flood protection. The Great Garuda provides a dramatic concept of a protected, rejuvenated Jakarta, but its feasibility and influence remain uncertain. (Abitare, 2016) This plan came on halt in October 2017 due to change in the ruling party. Currently there are just three artificial islands left out of the 17 that were initially intended. The building of a 46.212-kilometer coastal barrier along Jakarta's northern border is ongoing. On the other hand, to mitigate the principal source of soil sinking, the Jakarta municipality has sought to limit groundwater intake by large users. However, there is no alternate water source. The Jakarta administration is still unable to provide domestic water for the city's 9 million residents and an additional 15 million people who commute and work there every day. Addressing water scarcity is critical for conserving groundwater and slowing subsidence. There have been talks among the nation leaders to shift Indonesia's capital from Jakarta to some other safer and more suitable city.

Conclusion:

Jakarta being the capital city and one of the business capital cities of Indonesia, it is evident that the current situation is linked with haphazard development, in which high-density areas are the most affected and vulnerable areas. Furthermore, the unavailability of clean water, which leads to illegal groundwater extraction, has exaggerated the issue of land subsidence. To mitigate this issue, not only such technical solutions but community engagement is the key. Local initiative drive that promotes grassroots solutions, advocacy, and awareness towards the sensitive issue and environment. The government's involvement in social protection programs provides support to impacted populations, including healthcare, livelihood assistance, and relocation aid. Inclusive participation and planning ensure fair solutions by actively involving vulnerable communities in decision-making and addressing their specific needs in mitigation and adaptation efforts. By combining technical solutions with community engagement and social protection, a more resilient future for areas battling subsidence in Jakarta can be built.

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